

Ageing in the brain: mechanisms and rejuvenating strategies

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Highlights

- Ageing is the biggest risk factor for neurodegenerative diseases, with some brain regions being more vulnerable.
- The precise boundaries between healthy and pathological brain ageing are not fully understood
- Brain ageing is driven by both systemic and local factors.
- Rejuvenating interventions must address brain ageing

- 41 • Systemic rejuvenating strategies can delay brain ageing

42

43

44 **Abstract**

45 Ageing is characterised by the progressive loss of cellular homeostasis, leading to an
46 overall decline of the organism fitness. In the brain, ageing is highly associated with
47 cognitive decline and neurodegenerative diseases. With the rise in life expectancy,
48 characterising the brain ageing process becomes fundamental for developing
49 therapeutic interventions against the increased incidence of age-related
50 neurodegenerative diseases and to aim for an increase in human lifespan and, more
51 importantly, healthspan. In this review, we will start by introducing the
52 molecular/cellular hallmarks associated to brain ageing and their impact in brain cell
53 populations. Following, we will assess emerging evidence on how systemic ageing
54 translates into brain ageing. Finally, we will revise the mainstream and the novel
55 rejuvenating strategies, discussing the most successful ones in delaying brain ageing
56 and related diseases.

57

58 **Introduction**

59 Ageing is characterised by the accumulation of molecular and cellular damage over
60 an organismal lifespan, and is associated with physical deterioration and an increased
61 risk for developing diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders (Wyss-Coray,
62 2016). The inability to repair damage leads to impaired physiological functions,
63 ultimately leading to disease and death. Twelve hallmarks have been defined as
64 common denominators for mammalian ageing: genomic instability, telomere attrition,
65 epigenetic alterations, loss of proteostasis, disabled macroautophagy, deregulated
66 nutrient sensing, mitochondrial dysfunction, cellular senescence, stem cell
67 exhaustion, altered intercellular communication, chronic inflammation and dysbiosis
68 (Lopez-Otin *et al*, 2022). Interestingly, the established hallmarks of ageing are also
69 highly associated with an increased risk to develop neurodegenerative diseases (Hou
70 *et al*, 2019; Wyss-Coray, 2016).

71 Being composed by mitotic, but also by postmitotic cells, the brain is particularly
72 sensitive to the effects of ageing, manifested as structural and cognitive alterations
73 (Fjell & Walhovd, 2010; Grajauskas *et al*, 2019). With age, there is a natural
74 progressive decline in memory and learning capability, as well as decreased decision-
75 making speed, sensory perception, and motor coordination (Mattson & Arumugam,
76 2018). Whereas some individuals have a healthy brain ageing trajectory, many
77 develop age-associated diseases; in fact, the prevalence of neurodegenerative
78 hallmarks in the brains of older populations is extremely common, but the susceptibility

79 to developing age related diseases is greatly dependent on genetics and
80 environmental factors (Wyss-Coray, 2016).

81 The development of age-related neurodegenerative diseases has devastating effects
82 to the elder population, depriving individuals from their memories, disrupting their
83 social behaviour, and eventually taking their autonomy. Understanding the molecular
84 mechanisms behind brain ageing will support the development of strategies to delay
85 ageing and prevent or even treat age-related neurodegenerative diseases. In this
86 review, we present the current knowledge in the molecular mechanisms of ageing in
87 the brain, discuss how systemic ageing impacts the brain, and, finally, review the latest
88 published rejuvenating strategies and their impact in brain.

89 **Molecular mechanisms of brain ageing**

90 At a molecular and cellular level, several pathways and biomarkers are associated
91 with ageing; Lopez-Otin *et al.* described and categorised the hallmarks that reflect the
92 mammalian ageing process (Lopez-Otin *et al.*, 2022); the brain ageing hallmarks
93 (Mattson & Arumugam, 2018) mostly overlap with the classic ageing hallmarks
94 (Lopez-Otin *et al.*, 2013; Lopez-Otin *et al.*, 2022). The primary hallmarks cause damage
95 to cellular function, and include genomic instability, telomere attrition, epigenetic
96 alterations, loss of proteostasis and disabled macroautophagy. These are followed by
97 the secondary (or antagonistic) hallmarks, that are responses to damage, including
98 metabolism dysregulation: nutrient sensing, mitochondrial function impairment, and
99 cellular senescence. Finally, the tertiary, integrative hallmarks are triggered: these are
100 related to tissue homeostasis failures, and include stem cell exhaustion, impairment
101 of intercellular communication and chronic inflammation, which lead to systemic
102 decline and dysfunction (Figure 1).

103 ***Genomic instability, DNA damage, epigenetic changes and telomere attrition in*** 104 ***brain ageing***

105 DNA damage increases with age (Soto-Palma *et al.*, 2022). Postmitotic neurons, with
106 highly demanding energy requirements, elevated transcription, and long lifespan, are
107 highly susceptible to DNA damage. To counteract this, neurons are equipped with
108 efficient DNA damage response (DDR) pathways, but impairment or overwhelming
109 these pathways, due to ageing, leads to unrepaired DNA lesion accumulation,
110 resulting in genomic instability, transcription dysregulation, and, consequently, a
111 cascade of events culminating in cell senescence or cell death (Konopka & Atkin,
112 2022; Welch & Tsai, 2022). DNA damage is highly associated with neuronal
113 dysfunction and neurodegeneration, and is an early indicator of neuropathology (Chow
114 & Herrup, 2015; Konopka & Atkin, 2022; Shanbhag *et al.*, 2019; Simpson *et al.*, 2015;
115 Welch & Tsai, 2022). Additionally, although post-mitotic neurons are the most
116 susceptible, glial cells have also been shown to suffer pathological DNA damage
117 during ageing (Barzilai *et al.*, 2017; Palmer & Ousman, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2021; Zhang
118 *et al.*, 2021c).

119 Epigenetic modification during ageing is an emergent field (Bell *et al*, 2012; Hernandez
120 *et al*, 2011; Johnson *et al*, 2012). During ageing, DNA methylation sites change,
121 relatively consistently between individuals, allowing the identification of a series of
122 individual methylation sites, now called DNA methylation clocks, which can be used
123 as biomarkers of healthy ageing or disease risk, or determine the efficiency of
124 therapeutic interventions (Bell *et al*, 2019; Johnson *et al.*, 2012). These DNA
125 landscape modifications are linked to age-associated neurodegenerative diseases.
126 DNA methylation is associated with transcription repression (Johnson *et al.*, 2012),
127 which, in principle, can be highly detrimental; however, the exact role of DNA
128 methylation in brain ageing is still unknown, and it remains undetermined whether
129 methylation alterations are a cause or a consequence of ageing. Analysis of DNA
130 methylation patterns of different neurodegenerative disorders, such as Alzheimer's
131 disease (AD), dementia with Lewy bodies, Parkinson's disease (PD), and AD
132 associated with Down's syndrome, found similar DNA methylation landscapes
133 (Sanchez-Mut *et al*, 2016). More recently, a genome-wide DNA methylation meta-
134 analysis also found shared associations across neurodegenerative diseases (Nabais
135 *et al*, 2021).

136 Another well-defined hallmark of ageing is telomere attrition. Telomeres maintain
137 genomic stability by protecting chromosomal ends from degradation, with telomerase
138 having a crucial role in maintaining telomere length (Shay & Wright, 2019). With
139 ageing, accumulative cell divisions and exposure to stress leads to telomere
140 shortening; when a certain critical length is reached, cell-cycle arrests and the cell
141 becomes senescent (Rossiello *et al*, 2022). Senescent cells, as discussed in a
142 subsequent section, are highly detrimental (Levstek *et al*, 2020). In the brain, the
143 telomere attrition hallmark concept is challenging, as evidence is currently
144 inconsistent: literature describes telomere shortening and decreased telomerase
145 activity in aged microglia, but not in astrocytes (Flanary & Streit, 2004; Hu *et al*, 2021;
146 Saretzki, 2022); concerning neurons, recent literature shows that telomerase can
147 persist in adult neurons and also be induced by different insults (Liu *et al*, 2018;
148 Spilsbury *et al*, 2015). As expected, high telomerase activity is found in neuronal stem
149 cells niches in the adult brain (Levstek *et al.*, 2020), being essential for cell
150 proliferation, neuronal differentiation, neuronal survival, and neurogenesis (Liu *et al.*,
151 2018). Studies associating telomere shortening and cognitive performance, or even
152 neurodegenerative diseases, have been conflicting (Levstek *et al.*, 2020);
153 nevertheless, recent *in vivo* studies show a promising effect of telomerase in AD (Shim
154 *et al*, 2021; Spilsbury *et al.*, 2015) and PD models (Scheffold *et al*, 2016; Wan *et al*,
155 2021; Whitemore *et al*, 2019). Nonetheless, the importance of telomeres in brain
156 ageing and the development of neurodegenerative pathways is still poorly understood
157 and warrants further investigation.

158

159 **Loss of proteostasis**

160 Proteostasis is the mechanism of proteome homeostasis maintenance, regulating
161 protein turnover and structure. The accumulation and aggregation of misfolded and
162 unfolded proteins is characteristic of ageing, as observed with the accumulation
163 of myelin fragments in ageing glia (Safaiyan *et al*, 2016), and is believed to contribute
164 to progressive neuronal dysfunction and neurodegeneration (Espay *et al.*, 2019).

165 Proteostasis upregulation promotes synaptic plasticity (Zhu *et al*, 2019) and delays
166 age-related cognitive decline (Krukowski *et al*, 2020); this process is not limited to
167 neuronal cells, as decreasing autophagy in astrocytes and microglia compromises
168 synaptic function and impairs cognition (Kim *et al*, 2017).

169 In addition to protein deposits, other macromolecule complexes (including
170 carbohydrates and lipids) accumulate in the ageing brain, both extracellularly (such as
171 *corpora amylacea*) and inside neurons or glial cells (such as lipofuscin); the role of
172 these aggregates is not yet clear, but are believed to affect neuronal function (Moreno-
173 Garcia *et al*, 2018). Several age-related neurodegenerative disorders clearly
174 feature protein unfolding and aggregation, notably β -amyloid and Tau in AD, α -SYN in
175 PD, superoxide dismutase in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), huntingtin in
176 Huntington's disease (HD), or prion protein (PrP) in prion diseases, but although the
177 correlation between aggregation and disease is very well established, as we have
178 recently reviewed (Trigo *et al*, 2019), causality has not so easily been determined; in
179 fact, some of the neurons with aggregated inclusions were found not to be the ones
180 degenerating in HD, and vice versa (Kuemmerle *et al*, 1999; Vonsattel *et al*, 1985);
181 nonetheless, evidence suggests that improved proteostasis has beneficial effects in
182 ageing: upregulation of proteostasis via heat-shock proteins (Vos *et al*, 2016) or the
183 stress response pathway (Mark *et al*, 2016) increases lifespan and is being explored
184 as a cognitive-restoring therapy in dementia (Heard *et al*, 2018; Krukowski *et al.*,
185 2020).

186 Being highly correlated with neurodegeneration, the increased production and
187 impaired clearing of misfolded proteins results in accumulation of aggregated proteins
188 with ageing, but it remains a current issue of debate whether aggregation is just a
189 physiological consequence of ageing or is a direct contributor to ageing-related
190 pathology.

191 **Metabolic dysregulation**

192 Due to the brain's elevated energetic demands, it is particularly susceptible to
193 metabolic dysfunction impairment, and brain ageing is accompanied by decreased
194 glucose availability and mitochondrial activity (Mattson & Arumugam, 2018). The
195 recent bioenergetic hypothesis proposes that physiological ageing promotes
196 metabolic alterations, which then lead to cognitive decline and neurodegeneration
197 (Swerdlow, 2020); glucose metabolism and mitochondrial function are indeed

198 impaired in the brain of most neurodegenerative pathologies (Han *et al*, 2021; Wang
199 *et al*, 2019). Ageing-associated cognitive decline can be countered by metabolic
200 upregulation in myeloid cells (Minhas *et al*, 2021), and therapeutic approaches
201 targetting nutrient sensing are protective against cognitive decline (Kioussis *et al*,
202 2021).

203 Neurons consume 70%–80% of brain energy, requiring a continuous flow of blood
204 glucose as an energy source, regulated by blood–brain barrier (BBB) -located glucose
205 transporters (GLUT) (Camandola & Mattson, 2017). Impairment of mitochondria
206 activity during ageing results in hypometabolism and oxidative stress, and glucose
207 hypometabolism compromises protein and neurotransmitter synthesis (Harris *et al*,
208 2012). Brain cognitive processing is optimized by its metabolic needs, linking cognition
209 and energy. Indeed, network dysfunctions during cognitive ageing (aged neurons
210 notoriously feature reduced dendritic trees, with alterations to dendritic spine size,
211 shape, density, and turnover) are accompanied by metabolic dysfunction
212 (Kapogiannis & Mattson, 2011).

213 Although neurons are the most energetically demanding cells in the brain,
214 mitochondria dysfunction also affects ageing glial cells. Astrocytes are recognized to
215 play crucial roles in brain metabolism. Dysfunction of astrocytic mitochondria is linked
216 to age-related neurodegeneration (Wang & Xu, 2020) and to most age-related
217 neurodegenerative diseases (Gollihue & Norris, 2020). Astrocytic ageing features not
218 only reactive oxygen species (ROS) accumulation, but also Ca²⁺ overload (Ishii *et al*,
219 2017). The neuroprotective capacity of astrocytes decreases during ageing, as
220 antioxidative and mitophagic activity are decreased, while pro-inflammatory activity,
221 via microglial signal amplification, is increased (Ishii *et al*, 2017; Jiang & Cadenas,
222 2014; Wang & Xu, 2020).

223 Mitochondrial DNA damage accumulates in aged microglia, accompanied by impaired
224 autophagy, contributing to the accumulation of damaged mitochondria and
225 potentiating ROS production; in a positive feedback loop, increased mitochondrial
226 oxidative stress in turn activates the proinflammatory NF-κB, promoting microglial
227 ageing (Nakanishi & Wu, 2009); NF-κB inhibition in microglia has a neuroprotective
228 effect (Zaghloul *et al*, 2020), but it has yet to be explored in the context of ageing-
229 associated cognitive dysfunction.

230 Finally, oligodendrocytes are particularly metabolic demanding during myelination, but
231 their energy needs remain high, due to myelin maintenance and metabolic support of
232 neurons (Sams, 2021). Ageing-related mitochondrial loss of function is anticipated to
233 impair myelination, not only due to energy deficits and inefficient lipid syntthesis, but
234 also due to increased and cumulative ROS production, particularly damaging in terms
235 of myelin lipidic oxidation (Meyer & Rinholm, 2021).

236 Mitochondrial dysfunction is tightly associated with brain ageing (Yin *et al*, 2014), due
237 to the accumulation of oxidative damage (Cui *et al*, 2012; Floyd & Hensley, 2002), and

238 has been observed in hippocampal neurons (Kataoka *et al*, 2020) and linked with
239 ageing and HD (Becanovic *et al*, 2021). These facets are mechanically related, as age-
240 related loss of mitochondria function and efficiency results in increased neuronal
241 oxidative stress (Liguori *et al*, 2018), but at the same time impaired mitochondria
242 response to oxidative stress with ageing results in increased protein aggregation
243 (Trigo *et al*, 2022).

244 In parallel, ageing is also regulated by metabolic mechanisms. Nutrient signalling
245 regulates ageing and age-related neurodegeneration (Ondaro *et al*, 2022) via the
246 signalling pathways of the growth hormone (GH) / insulin-like growth factor (IGF), the
247 mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR), sirtuins, and 5' AMP-activated protein kinase
248 (AMPK) (Pan & Finkel, 2017; Sadria & Layton, 2021).

249 Signalling of the GH/IGF axis declines with ageing (Zadik *et al*, 1985) and its inhibition
250 appears to promote brain health in ageing, by increasing stress resistance, regulating
251 metabolism, and reducing inflammation. IGF1 may have opposing effects in the
252 ageing brain, depending on context: its inhibition appears to be neuroprotective
253 against protein aggregation (via proteostasis upregulation), but IGF1 silencing is on
254 the other hand linked to cognitive dysfunction and neurovascular disruption (Gubbi *et al*,
255 2018). Balancing this dual effect is required to efficiently develop therapeutic
256 strategies.

257 mTOR is a serine-threonine kinase signal integrator (Saxton & Sabatini, 2017) that
258 can influence longevity and ageing (Sadria & Layton, 2021), highly expressed in
259 neurons and glia (Perluigi *et al*, 2015). Its role in energy metabolism, autophagy, and
260 proteostasis regulation (Guillen & Benito, 2018) is essential for brain homeostasis
261 during ageing (O' Neill, 2013). Systemic mTOR activity increases during ageing,
262 impairing autophagy (Laplante & Sabatini, 2012), but is decreased in the ageing
263 hippocampus (Yang *et al*, 2014), and research is clarifying its role in the ageing brain.

264 Sirtuins ameliorate autophagy, neuroinflammation (Sato *et al*, 2017), and
265 mitochondrial dysfunction in the ageing brain (Steiner *et al*, 2011). Sirtuin levels
266 diminish with ageing (Grabowska *et al*, 2017) and, together with mTOR, are promising
267 targets to increase lifespan (Wang *et al*, 2016).

268 Tightly related to the previous signalling pathways, AMPK is believed to slow down
269 ageing and increase lifespan by modulating the mitochondrial network (Weir *et al*,
270 2017), with its signalling declining with age. AMPK upregulates brain derived
271 neurotrophic factor (BDNF), essential for synaptic transmission and memory
272 consolidation (Miranda *et al*, 2019) and plays neuroprotective roles by mitigating
273 neuroinflammation and oxidative stress (Zhao *et al*, 2019), being explored as a clinical
274 target to promote longevity, namely with the use of metformin (Ma *et al*, 2022) or
275 rapamycin (Sun *et al*, 2019).

276 Age-related metabolic and mitochondrial regulators are becoming increasingly
277 established as key triggers for cognitive decline and are potential future therapeutic
278 strategies (de Lucia *et al*, 2020).

279 ***Cellular senescence in the aged brain***

280 Originally described as an irreversible cell cycle arrest in proliferative cells (Hayflick,
281 1965), cellular senescence can be elicited by various intrinsic and extrinsic stimuli and
282 developmental signals (Kumari & Jat, 2021), but most importantly, their abundance is
283 increased in ageing and progeroid syndromes (Jeyapalan & Sedivy, 2008). Senescent
284 cells undergo alterations in morphology, gene expression (transcriptional and
285 epigenetic alterations), and metabolic activity; these cells are characterised by chronic
286 inflammation, heightened oxidative stress, persistent DNA damage response, cell
287 cycle arrest, and chromatin reorganization, developing a senescence-associated
288 secretory phenotype (SASP) (Lopes-Paciencia *et al*, 2019). SASP is characterized by
289 cytokine, chemokine, growth factor, and protease secretion (Birch & Gil, 2020), and
290 senescent cells have a pleiotropic effect on tissue microenvironment via these
291 remodelling factors, inducing chronic sterile inflammation, leading to detrimental
292 phenotypes in nearby cells and tissue dysfunction, and contributing to age-related
293 diseases (Tchkonia *et al*, 2013).

294 Removal of senescent cells was shown to increase life span in mouse models (Baker
295 *et al*, 2016; Baker *et al*, 2011). In the brain, various cell populations, including
296 astrocytes, microglia, and oligodendrocytes present senescence (Sahu *et al*, 2022;
297 Sikora *et al*, 2021). Neurons are of particular interest: being non-mitotic, they exhibit a
298 senescence-like phenotype associated with ageing and neurodegenerative
299 phenotypes (Dehkordi *et al*, 2021; Jurk *et al*, 2012; Musi *et al*, 2018; Riessland *et al*,
300 2019), but since cellular senescence was first described as a permanent cell cycle
301 arrest, the first evidence of neuronal senescence features was puzzling. Nevertheless,
302 several independent studies have described a senescence-like behaviour and
303 senescence biomarkers in neurons (Dehkordi *et al.*, 2021; Jurk *et al.*, 2012; Musi *et*
304 *al.*, 2018; Riessland *et al.*, 2019), although their molecular mechanisms of induction
305 remain poorly understood.

306 It is also important to mention the increased senescence in stem cell niches during
307 ageing, including in the brain (Nicaise *et al*, 2020), an important contributor for
308 neurogenerative diseases and cognitive impairment (Costantini *et al*, 2018).

309 Cellular senescence can trigger neurodegeneration via an array of mechanisms,
310 including inflammation, through SASP, but also mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative
311 stress, disrupted protein homeostasis, and compromised nuclear and blood brain
312 barrier (BBB) integrity. By persisting in the brain, senescent cells contribute to
313 cognitive decline by impairing synaptic function, inducing paracrine inflammation and
314 senescence. Growing evidence points to a close association between senescence
315 and neurodegenerative diseases, such as AD and PD (Bhat *et al*, 2012; Chinta *et al*,

316 2018; Dehkordi *et al.*, 2021; Gaikwad *et al.*, 2021; Hu *et al.*, 2021; Si *et al.*, 2021; Verma
317 *et al.*, 2021; Yoon *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2019), and eliminating senescent cells,
318 using senolytics, not only improves brain ageing phenotypes (Fielder *et al.*, 2022;
319 Krzystyniak *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2021a), but is also beneficial in several models
320 of neurogenerative diseases (Baker & Petersen, 2018; Baker *et al.*, 2011; Bussian *et*
321 *al.*, 2018; Chinta *et al.*, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2019).

322 ***Stem cell exhaustion in brain ageing***

323 One of the most striking characteristics of ageing is the loss of tissue regenerative
324 capability, with evidence suggesting a correlation between stem cell dysfunction, DNA
325 damage accumulation, telomere shortening, and senescence (Lopez-Otin *et al.*,
326 2013). In the brain, adult neurogenesis is limited to the subgranular zone (SGZ) in the
327 hippocampal dentate gyrus, and the subventricular zone (SVZ) of the lateral ventricles,
328 and it is compromised during ageing, with decreased and more dormant neural stem
329 cells, decreased neuronal fate commitment, and decreased self-renewal and survival
330 (Navarro Negredo *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, aged neural stem cells present hallmarks
331 of ageing, including epigenetic alterations, proteostasis dysregulation, senescence,
332 and inflammation (Nicaise *et al.*, 2020).

333 In rodents, loss in neurogenesis is observed early in the mature brain (Ben Abdallah
334 *et al.*, 2010; Daynac *et al.*, 2016; Ibrayeva *et al.*, 2021), but the concept of neurogenesis
335 decline in humans is controversial (Kempermann *et al.*, 2018). While some studies
336 describe a drop in neurogenesis in adult human brains (Sorrells *et al.*, 2018), others
337 report stable neurogenesis in older, healthy individuals (Boldrini *et al.*, 2018). More
338 recently, neural stem cell subpopulations were shown to undergo asynchronous
339 decline exhibiting early molecular ageing (Ibrayeva *et al.*, 2021). Neurogenesis
340 impairment with age was shown to accompany a decrease in learning and memory (Li
341 *et al.*, 2022; McAvoy *et al.*, 2016; Navarro Negredo *et al.*, 2020), cognitive impairment,
342 and neurodegenerative diseases (Culig *et al.*, 2022), one example of which is the
343 evidence of reduced neurogenesis in AD (Moreno-Jimenez *et al.*, 2019; Tobin *et al.*,
344 2019). Even though there are inconsistent reports linking neurogenesis and cognition
345 (Babcock *et al.*, 2021; Li Puma *et al.*, 2020), a potential role in age-related
346 neurodegeneration can be proposed.

347 ***Impairment of intercellular communication***

348 Ageing features chronic low inflammation (inflammaging) due to the accumulation of
349 tissue damage, dysfunction of the immune system, accumulation of pro-inflammatory
350 cytokine secreting senescent cells, and defects in the autophagy system (Lopez-Otin
351 *et al.*, 2013).

352 Glia, the proliferative population of brain, is thought to be the main contributing
353 component for inflammaging in the aged brain, as both astrocytes and microglia
354 become more senescent with ageing, experiencing an increase in inflammatory profile

355 and dysfunction (Costa *et al*, 2021; Lopez-Teros *et al*, 2022). Glial dysfunction impacts
356 normal brain homeostasis and is associated with cognitive decline through
357 senescence and proinflammatory secretory mediators (Costa *et al.*, 2021; Lopez-
358 Teros *et al.*, 2022). Age-related brain inflammation induces synaptic alterations and
359 changes in neuronal function (Lopez-Teros *et al.*, 2022; Simen *et al*, 2011; Trivino &
360 von Bernhardt, 2021), but the mechanism leading to cognitive impairment during
361 ageing is multifactorial; nevertheless, inflammaging seems to have a significant role
362 in age-related cognitive decline and the development of neurodegenerative diseases
363 (Calabrese *et al*, 2018; Magalhaes *et al*, 2021; Stephenson *et al*, 2018; Trivino & von
364 Bernhardt, 2021).

365 Waste clearance is essential for brain homeostasis and function. With ageing, the
366 mechanisms responsible for clearing metabolic by-products and cellular debris are
367 compromise; this impairment is associated with cognitive alteration and
368 neurodegeneration (Costea *et al*, 2019; Kylkilahti *et al*, 2021; Silva *et al*, 2021).

369 The brain lacks a conventional lymphatic system, but a novel system for brain waste
370 clearance was recently described, the glymphatic (glial-lymphatic) system, that
371 facilitates the metabolic clearance in the central nervous system (CNS) through the
372 flow of interstitial and cerebrospinal fluid via perivascular pathways, controlled by
373 astrocytes, specifically the astrocytic aquaporin-4 (Gordleeva *et al*, 2020). Glymphatic
374 clearance is reduced in aged mice (Kress *et al*, 2014) and humans (Zhou *et al*, 2020),
375 and seems to be essential to clear neurotoxic protein aggregates, with its impairment
376 favouring neurodegeneration (Gordleeva *et al.*, 2020). Besides the glymphatic system,
377 the CNS has other mechanisms of clearance, such as cellular uptake and transport
378 across the BBB (Kaur *et al*, 2021). The dysfunction of neural cells observed in ageing
379 will surely impact their ability to manage and clear waste; additionally, BBB is also
380 compromised in ageing (Hussain *et al*, 2021). Waste accumulation can potentiate the
381 activation of immune cells in the brain, raising its pro-inflammatory status (Gordleeva
382 *et al.*, 2020).

383 Impairment of the adaptive stress response signalling and aberrant neuronal network
384 activity are other crucial markers of brain ageing (Mattson & Arumugam, 2018).
385 Because cells are constantly exposed to metabolic, ionic, and oxidative stresses,
386 cellular stress, response systems were developed to adapt to stresses, alleviate the
387 danger, and improve cell defence to future stress (Mattson & Arumugam, 2018).
388 Calcium, ATP levels, and ROS are triggers of these responses.

389 During ageing, neuronal capability to regulate calcium dynamics is compromised
390 (Mattson & Arumugam, 2018). The major causes of neuronal calcium dysregulation
391 during ageing are ER stress, altered mitochondria homeostasis, dysregulated calcium
392 channels' activity, and altered levels of calcium binding proteins (Chandran *et al*,
393 2019).

394 Calcium is extremely important for regulating neuronal function, plasticity, synaptic
395 transmission and to integrate neuronal networks; moreover, calcium is crucial for ER
396 and mitochondria homeostasis, hence impairment of calcium dynamics is linked to
397 neuropathology vulnerability (Chandran *et al.*, 2019) and critical for cognition (Toescu
398 & Verkhratsky, 2007). Importantly, a continued increase in intracellular calcium levels
399 can damage and kill neurons by activating calcium-dependent apoptosis (Chandran
400 *et al.*, 2019; Mattson & Arumugam, 2018); restoring neuronal calcium homeostasis is
401 enough to revert cognitive alterations in aged mice (Gant *et al.*, 2015).

402 The age-dependent decline in cell metabolism results in disruption of brain energy
403 homeostasis, with faulty neuronal glucose metabolism and ATP deficits (Mattson &
404 Arumugam, 2018). The general energy deficiency leads to impaired energy-requiring
405 mechanisms, such as calcium pump activity, transcription, and protein production.
406 Additionally, ATP and calcium pumps are extremely important pieces in neuronal
407 network activity, being crucial for action potential conduction and synaptic activity, and,
408 ultimately, cognitive function (Blaszczyk, 2020).

409 The increase in ROS production due to mitochondria dysfunction, discussed in a
410 previous section, leads to changes in the redox state of the cell, including the oxidative
411 state of DNA, altering transcription factor responsiveness and even protein production
412 and function (Mattson & Arumugam, 2018). This is intricately linked to age-associated
413 cognitive decline (Kandlur *et al.*, 2020), with antioxidants having a neuroprotective
414 effect (Franzoni *et al.*, 2021).

415 Another consequence of ageing is the loss of white matter, with evidence of decreased
416 myelination with age caused by oligodendrocyte oxidative DNA damage (Tse &
417 Herrup, 2017). Since communication between different brain regions occurs
418 preferentially via myelinated axonal projections, myelination defects are surely
419 detrimental for the network, leading to increased risk of neurological diseases (Filley
420 & Fields, 2016; Tse & Herrup, 2017).

421 Evidence shows that brain structure integrity (with appropriate types of neurons,
422 functional glia, and reliable neurotransmitter systems) is essential for the correct brain
423 circuit function; ageing disturbs both cellular local mechanisms and circuit networks
424 within the brain, leading to cognitive dysfunction.

425 **Differential neural vulnerability to ageing**

426 Ageing is the leading risk factor for neurodegenerative diseases, but the precise
427 boundaries between healthy and pathological brain ageing are not well defined.
428 Genetic, epigenetic, and environmental factors are contributors to human ageing, and
429 humans age at different rates (Belsky *et al.*, 2015). In fact, recent evidence indicates
430 that organs also age at different rates (Nie *et al.*, 2022; Schaum *et al.*, 2020), which
431 unlocks the question why some organs and systems are more vulnerable than others.
432 In the case of the brain, it is well known that neurodegenerative diseases, such as AD,

433 PD, and ALS, present region-specific neurodegeneration; however, it is still unknown
434 why some brain regions are more vulnerable to neurodegeneration (Pandya & Patani,
435 2021). In the case of physiologic ageing, evidence shows increased vulnerability of
436 white matter (primarily myelinated axons) to age (Bender *et al*, 2016), certainly leading
437 to functional consequences (Filley & Fields, 2016). Interestingly, the prefrontal cortex
438 and the hippocampus display a significant decrease in volume with age (Dotson *et al*,
439 2015; Jernigan *et al*, 2001), indicating a possible higher susceptibility to ageing.

440 The alteration of cerebral blood flow during healthy ageing is a concept still needing
441 further studies, but there are some indicators that cerebral blood flow is altered in
442 ageing, exposing different brain regions to hypoxia, possibly increasing their risk of
443 neurodegeneration (Pandya & Patani, 2021).

444 Looking in more detail to the brain, each region comprises various types of neural
445 cells, differing from region to region. This regional heterogeneity may underlie the
446 different regional susceptibility to age-related alterations. The hippocampus has an
447 interesting characteristic: it presents neural stem cells in the subgranular zone of the
448 dentate gyrus (Navarro Negredo *et al.*, 2020), which decline in ageing, with functional
449 implications in learning and memory (Ibrayeva *et al.*, 2021). This unique characteristic
450 can render the hippocampus a higher susceptibility to age-related decline.

451 Age-related neuronal loss has been shown in the hippocampus and the substantia
452 nigra (Bettio *et al*, 2017; Pandya & Patani, 2021; Rudow *et al*, 2008), supporting the
453 notion of increased hippocampal and substantia nigral susceptibility to age-related
454 dysfunction; interestingly, large sized neurons with lengthy axons tend to be more
455 vulnerable to ageing (Mattson & Magnus, 2006), which agrees with neuronal features
456 of the hippocampus and substantia nigra (Pandya & Patani, 2021).

457 An alternative theory concerning neuronal vulnerability proposes that age-related
458 mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress surge are the main culprits behind the
459 varying neuronal sensitivity, with some neurons, such as hippocampal and substantia
460 nigral ones, being more sensitive to this damage (Wang & Michaelis, 2010). Besides
461 neurons, glia was shown to present differential age-associated regional alterations
462 (Soreq *et al*, 2017). Consistently, hippocampal and substantia nigral astrocytes seem
463 more susceptible to ageing, in terms of number, proinflammatory reactivity, and
464 protective capacity, whereas microglia seem to present more age-related alterations
465 in the hippocampus (Pandya & Patani, 2021).

466 Additionally, the size and thickness of the prefrontal cortex was also shown to
467 decrease with age (Dotson *et al.*, 2015). The prefrontal cortex plays an important role
468 in cognition, including attention and memory, and is interconnected with subcortical
469 regions, such as thalamus, amygdala, and hippocampus, exerting control over other
470 brain regions involved in cognitive function (Jobson *et al*, 2021). Neuronal number in
471 some areas of the prefrontal cortex of non-primate humans was found reduced and
472 associated with memory impairment (Smith *et al*, 2004). However, more recent

473 literature suggests that cognition alteration due to changes in the prefrontal cortex are
474 more likely due to changes in neuronal density and synaptic plasticity and function
475 than to neuronal loss (Burke & Barnes, 2006; Morrison & Baxter, 2012). Concerning
476 glial cells, both microglia and astrocytes are activated in the aged prefrontal cortex,
477 correlating with synaptic dysfunction (Chan *et al*, 2018; Wruck & Adjaye, 2020).

478 The use of single cell transcriptomic profiling technology to depict changes in brain
479 ageing is an emerging trend that could greatly improve the current understanding of
480 brain complexity and specific cell type and regional vulnerability observed in ageing
481 and age-related pathology. Comparing young and old brains produced comprehensive
482 datasets of ageing-related genes, pathways, and interactions of different neural cell
483 types. In one such recent study, authors concluded that ageing, rather than inducing
484 a universal program, leads to distinct transcriptional courses in different cell
485 populations (Ximerakis *et al*, 2019). More recently, using spatially resolved single-cell
486 transcriptomics, a new high-resolution cell atlas of brain ageing depicted the changes
487 in gene expression and spatial organization of major cell types in the frontal cortex
488 and striatum over the mouse life-span (Allen *et al*, 2022), while other reports on single-
489 cell transcriptomics highlight transcriptional alterations in different cell types during
490 ageing (Chen *et al*, 2022; Luquez *et al*, 2022). Moreover, high-resolution ageing clocks
491 from single-cell transcriptomic data were very recently proposed (Buckley *et al*, 2022)
492 and will allow the quantification of transcriptomic rejuvenation of therapeutic
493 interventions. In coming years, research using these newly developed technologies
494 will surely help disclose the complex question of why brain regions have differential
495 vulnerability to ageing, opening new venues for rejuvenating therapies.

496 **Impact of systemic ageing in brain health**

497 Besides cell-intrinsic defects in neurons and glia, leading to brain dysfunction due to
498 age-related damage accumulation, systemic factors may also contribute to brain
499 dysfunction and decline with age (Figure 2). Since tissues and organs age at different
500 rates (Nie *et al.*, 2022; Schaum *et al.*, 2020), it is possible that some tissues influence
501 others' ageing decline. Several pivotal studies reveal that young blood or bone marrow
502 transplantation reverse age-related cognitive dysfunction and recover synaptic
503 plasticity (Das *et al*, 2019; Katsimpardi *et al*, 2014; Villeda *et al*, 2014). Additionally,
504 whole body clearance of senescent cells was enough to ameliorate age-related brain
505 inflammation and cognitive impairment in mice; however, this study targeted whole-
506 body, and it is thus unknown whether the cognitive improvement is a result of
507 senescence clearance in the CNS or in peripheral organs (Ogrodnik *et al*, 2021). Other
508 systemic manipulations, such as exercise (Pereira *et al*, 2019) and caloric restriction
509 (Garcia-Matas *et al*, 2015; Hofer *et al*, 2008), show promising results. These systemic
510 rejuvenating approaches, especially the ones using young blood or bone marrow
511 transplantation, are strongly consistent with the idea that systemic ageing can induce
512 brain dysfunction.

513 Experimentally, the mechanistic study of how peripheral ageing leads to brain ageing
514 is complex, as separating the periphery from the brain, in respect to mechanisms or
515 interventions, is difficult. Nonetheless, some peripheral mediators of ageing are known
516 to impact the brain, in particular pro-inflammatory mediators. Age-related systemic
517 inflammation (inflammaging) is well documented to impact brain health and cognition
518 (Lutshumba *et al*, 2021). The role of the gut in inflammaging is now well recognized;
519 having the ability to secrete inflammatory products, the gut can affect other systems
520 and organs, accelerating their ageing-associated decline (Franceschi *et al*, 2018). The
521 gut and the brain establish a bidirectional connection: the gut - brain axis, established
522 through the vagus nerve, the immune system, and bacterial metabolites and products.
523 Research indicates that inflammatory gut metabolites impact brain cognition and
524 psychiatric symptoms, also seemingly accelerating neurodegenerative diseases (Mou
525 *et al*, 2022; Rutsch *et al*, 2020). Nevertheless, the mechanisms behind the impact of
526 gut microbiota in brain diseases are still poorly understood and need further
527 investigations.

528 The brain is protected from the periphery by the BBB, a selective, semipermeable
529 interface between the blood and the brain, with a crucial role in maintaining brain
530 homeostasis by controlling the selective crossing of needed molecules and exclusion
531 of toxins and pathogens. Correct BBB function requires a proper association between
532 brain endothelial cells, mural cells (pericytes and vascular smooth muscle cells),
533 astrocytes, neurons, microglia, and the basal lamina (Daneman & Prat, 2015). During
534 ageing, this barrier is disrupted (Figure 3), leaving the brain less protected, with
535 evidence suggesting that normal breakdown (due to healthy ageing) is only
536 detrimental following an exposure to secondary stress, such as inflammation, following
537 which cognitive decline emerges (Knox *et al*, 2022). It remains unclear how gut
538 metabolites, inflammatory mediators, and other factors access the brain, but the BBB
539 disruption caused by these inflammatory mediators is a possibility, alongside ageing-
540 related BBB dysfunction and breakdown due to cell dysfunction. Pericytes, BBB
541 transporters capable of sensing peripheral inflammation, may play a particularly
542 central role, as pericyte loss leads to immunogenic protein leakage into the brain, and
543 intact pericytes can also transduce inflammatory cues from the systemic environment
544 (Pluvinage & Wyss-Coray, 2020).

545 Another mechanism for metabolites and other factors to reach the brain is through the
546 blood–cerebral spinal fluid (CSF) barrier. In the choroid plexus, the close proximity of
547 blood to the CSF can possibly lead to choroid secretory function and CSF composition
548 modulation, with the blood–CSF barrier being a crucial transducer of systemic factors
549 for the modulation of brain ageing. Interestingly, infusion of young CSF into aged
550 brains restores oligodendrogenesis and improves memory in aged mice (Iram *et al*,
551 2022). Direct peripheral immune cell infiltration into the brain via the choroid plexus
552 has also been hypothesised, but further investigation is needed in the specific case of
553 healthy ageing (Pluvinage & Wyss-Coray, 2020).

554 **Impact of rejuvenating strategies in brain function**

555 Even though ageing and death are inevitabilities, strategies to delay and potentially
556 reverse ageing must be developed, with the aim to increase lifespan, but more
557 importantly, to improve healthspan, which include the maintenance of cognitive health
558 in the elderly and in the end of life. Systemic rejuvenating strategies that impact
559 several organs and tissues, including the brain, will be pivotal. Next, we will review
560 rejuvenating strategies with a known positive impact in brain ageing and cognition
561 (Figure 4).

562 ***Heterochronic parabiosis***

563 Heterochronic parabiosis provides evidence that blood factors influence organismal
564 ageing. In heterochronic parabiosis, the circulating systems of young and aged mouse
565 are fused, aiming to manipulate the plasma proteome of the older animals. Exposure
566 to old blood via heterochronic parabiosis or by administering old blood plasma
567 decreases hippocampal neurogenesis, decreases synaptic plasticity, promotes
568 microgliosis, and impairs learning and memory (Villeda *et al*, 2011), whereas exposing
569 aged mice to young blood enhances hippocampal neurogenesis (Katsimpardi *et al.*,
570 2014; Villeda *et al.*, 2014) and increases dendritic spine density, improving learning
571 and memory (Villeda *et al.*, 2014). These results suggested the presence of “pro-
572 cognitive” factors in young blood, and GDF11 was indeed found to mimic the effects
573 of young blood in enhancing neurogenesis (Katsimpardi *et al.*, 2014). Another factor,
574 the tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 2 (TIMP2), a blood-borne factor enriched in
575 human umbilical cord plasma, was shown to improve synaptic plasticity and
576 hippocampal-dependent cognition in aged mice (Castellano *et al*, 2017).

577 The transplantation of young bone marrow was shown to rejuvenate the hematopoietic
578 system, preserving cognitive function in old mice (Das *et al.*, 2019), while exposure to
579 an old hematopoietic system was enough to elicit a decrease in hippocampal synaptic
580 density and age-related cognitive impairment (Smith *et al*, 2020), defining the
581 importance of the hematopoietic system in rejuvenation strategies for brain function.
582 A different work showed osteocalcin to be necessary for the beneficial effect of young
583 plasma in memory and anxiety-like behaviours in old mice, identifying it as another
584 “pro-cognitive” young plasma factor (Khrimian *et al*, 2017); thrombospondin-4 and
585 SPARCL1, present in blood, were also found to mediate the beneficial effects of young
586 blood in *in vitro* synapse formation (Gan & Sudhof, 2019). Additionally, both C–C motif
587 chemokine ligand 11 (CCL11) and β 2-microglobulin have been described as pro-
588 ageing blood factors (Das *et al.*, 2019).

589 While the administration of old blood leads to impaired cognition (Villeda *et al.*, 2011),
590 the question of how this occurs remains unsolved; a recent study implicated the
591 vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1): systemic administration of anti-VCAM1
592 antibody or genetic ablation of *Vcam1* in brain endothelial cells of the BBB was able

593 to counteract the effects of old plasma, reverting microglial reactivity and cognitive
594 deficits (Yousef *et al*, 2019).

595 Research in parabiosis, young plasma administration, and pro-ageing / pro-youthful
596 blood factors has demonstrated the potential that changing old blood composition in
597 the periphery can have on cognitive function. This represents a potential for
598 therapeutic avenues aimed at restoring CNS functions by promoting a more youthful
599 systemic environment.

600 **Exercise**

601 Exercise is a well-established modulator of beneficial effects in brain, improving
602 neurogenesis, brain plasticity, and cognitive function, being protective for
603 neurodegeneration (Mandolesi *et al*, 2018; van Praag *et al*, 2005; Voss *et al*, 2019).
604 The positive effects of exercise are, in part, mediated by changes in the systemic
605 environment. The skeletal muscle undergoes dramatic changes due to exercise and
606 secretes a wide variety of molecules, including myokines, that can affect other organs
607 (Pluvinage & Wyss-Coray, 2020). Lactate, a metabolite that accumulates with
608 exercise, promotes brain angiogenesis, a possible contributor to cognitive
609 maintenance during normal ageing (Morland *et al*, 2017). Additionally, elevated levels
610 of circulating vascular endothelial growth factor and IGF1 due to exercise were shown
611 to mediate neurogenesis (Fabel *et al*, 2003; Trejo *et al*, 2001).

612 Liver metabolism also endures brain-modulating alterations during prolonged
613 exercise: under glucose depletion, ketones are produced, including the BBB-crossing
614 β -hydroxybutyrate, which was shown to induce BDNF expression in the hippocampus
615 (Sleiman *et al*, 2016). BDNF is a trophic factor associated with synaptic plasticity,
616 cognitive improvement, and the alleviation of depression and anxiety (Miranda *et al*,
617 2019). Recently, other liver-derived soluble factors released during exercise were
618 found to lead to neurogenesis and cognitive improvements on the aged brain
619 (Horowitz *et al*, 2020), and several protein and peptide myokines were shown to
620 regulate brain function, such as cathepsin B, clusterin, and Irisin (Pluvinage & Wyss-
621 Coray, 2020).

622 Exercise also acts directly in the brain, namely by enhancing neurogenesis (van Praag
623 *et al*, 2005), enhancing autophagy (Andreotti *et al*, 2020), promoting proteostasis
624 (Ross *et al*, 2019), increasing neurotransmitter levels (Lin & Kuo, 2013), and
625 maintaining the BBB, the neurovascular unit, and promoting glymphatic clearance
626 (Vecchio *et al*, 2018). It can also be beneficial for cognition by altering epigenetic
627 markers, such as DNA methylation, histone modifications, and microRNAs (miRNAs),
628 thus having a positive effect in brain ageing and age-related neurodegenerative
629 diseases (Fernandes *et al*, 2017).

630 Exercise has the potential to modulate the local brain environment directly and via
631 systemic targeting, and is a plausible effective strategy to reverse the functional
632 impairments of ageing in the CNS.

633 **Caloric Restriction**

634 A reduction of 20 to 40% of caloric intake was shown to counteract age-associated
635 phenotypes, increasing lifespan and healthspan across a spectrum of species
636 (Masoro, 2005), including humans (Flanagan *et al*, 2020).

637 How dietary caloric restriction increases lifespan and healthspan is not yet fully
638 characterized; however, metabolic increase, reduction of oxidative stress, and
639 increased ability to counteract DNA damage, as well as beneficial immune and
640 neuroendocrine effects, may be responsible (Bouchard & Villeda, 2015). In fact,
641 caloric restriction is generally accepted to alter the activity of common key metabolic
642 pathways, namely mTOR, IGF, and sirtuins (Pan & Finkel, 2017), and to decrease
643 oxidative damage to cellular macromolecules (including mitochondrial DNA) (Gredilla
644 & Barja, 2005). Moreover, age-related DNA oxidative damage is significantly reduced
645 by caloric restriction, that acts on DNA repair by enhancing pathways such as NER,
646 BER, and double-strand break repair (Heydari *et al*, 2007). A role for caloric restriction
647 in immune regulation and ameliorating immunosenescence has been shown in mice
648 (Asami *et al*, 2022) and in humans (Spadaro *et al*, 2022), with beneficial effects in
649 stem cell function (Cerletti *et al*, 2012; Ertl *et al*, 2008; Yilmaz *et al*, 2012).

650 While caloric restriction can enhance all of these pathways, it is evident that it also
651 enhances neural plasticity and cognition, reducing vulnerability to age-related neuro-
652 dysfunction and disease (Mattson, 2010). Caloric restriction was shown to mitigate
653 age-related loss of neurogenesis in the brain, preventing senescence increase
654 normally observed in the subventricular zone of the aged mouse brain, while
655 simultaneously diminishing age-related microglia activation and pro-inflammatory
656 cytokine increase (Apple *et al*, 2019) and promoting senescent astrocyte rejuvenation
657 (Garcia-Matas *et al.*, 2015). This dietary intervention is also beneficial for oxidative
658 stress: it attenuates the age-related increase in neuronal plasmalemma lipid
659 peroxidation, protein carbonyls, and nitrotyrosine (Hyun *et al*, 2006), and reduces
660 oxidative modifications in mitochondrial DNA, extremely beneficial for maintaining
661 mitochondria function (Gredilla & Barja, 2005). Overall, the decrease in oxidative
662 stress is clearly neuroprotective (Franzoni *et al.*, 2021); additionally, caloric restriction
663 positively alters the levels of neurotrophic factors, such as BDNF and glial cell line-
664 derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF), and increases the expression of IGF1 (Zhang *et*
665 *al*, 2021b); these factors together surely have a positive effect in neuronal health and
666 even neurogenesis.

667 Recently, as epigenetics have been granted more attention, the effect of caloric
668 restriction in epigenetics was explored. Studies found that caloric restriction can

669 positively alter epigenetic marks in the brain associated with ageing, protecting
670 neuronal health (Allison *et al*, 2021; Hadad *et al*, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2021b).

671 **Counteracting senescence**

672 The negative effects of cellular senescence are both local and systemic, due to its
673 paracrine effect via SASP. Senotherapeutics targeting senescent cells have emerged
674 as a strategy to fight ageing and age-related diseases. Senotherapies include
675 senolytics, which selectively kill senescent cells, senomorphics, which promote
676 senescent cells to behave as young cells or delay senescence progression, and
677 immune-system mediators, that stimulate senescent cells clearance (Kim & Kim,
678 2019). In the CNS, senolytic approaches have been shown to decrease the
679 senescence burden and improve cognitive performance and healthspan in ageing and
680 neurodegenerative mouse models (Lee *et al*, 2021; Sikora *et al.*, 2021). Elimination of
681 senescent cells, using an inducible p16-3MR transgenic mouse model which
682 abrogated senescence cells, was shown to improve age-related PD phenotypes,
683 including motor deficits, selective dopaminergic midbrain neuron loss, and reduced
684 neurogenesis (Chinta *et al.*, 2018). More recently, genetic and pharmacologic
685 elimination of whole-body senescent cells were shown to decrease brain inflammation
686 and cognitive impairment in aged mice (Ogrodnik *et al.*, 2021). Interestingly,
687 genetically eliminating systemic p16-senescent cells partially restores immune cell
688 activation and infiltration to youth levels, correlated with cognitive preservation (Zhang
689 *et al*, 2022). Additionally, heterochronic parabiosis decreases the burden of
690 senescence in several tissues, including the brain (Yousefzadeh *et al*, 2020), while
691 plasma dilution can similarly attenuate brain senescence and inflammation, improving
692 cognition (Mehdipour *et al*, 2021).

693 Nonetheless, it is important to mention the physiological role of senescence in tissue
694 regeneration, homeostasis (Da Silva-Alvarez *et al*, 2020), and in mammalian
695 embryonic development (Munoz-Espin *et al*, 2013). In this regard, a senostatic
696 approach using senomorphics (Kang, 2019) to prevent senescence accrual should be
697 considered for studies in brain ageing. One such approach is the overexpression of
698 forkhead box M1 transcription factor, that has a senomorphic effect and increases
699 healthspan in mice (Ribeiro *et al*, 2022), however little is known about its effects in the
700 brain.

701 **Cellular Reprogramming**

702 Using transcription factors, it is currently possible to convert somatic cells into
703 pluripotent stem cells (Takahashi & Yamanaka, 2006; Yu *et al*, 2007). With
704 reprogramming, a global remodelling of the epigenetic landscape of the cells is
705 possible, and rejuvenation a possibility. Considering reprogramming as an anti-ageing
706 strategy, somatic cells could be turned into pluripotent stem cells, which could then be
707 modified or corrected before redifferentiation, generating rejuvenated cells. Two
708 opportunities arise from cell reprogramming: *in vitro* rejuvenated cells or tissues to

709 replace damaged tissues and organs, and direct reprogramming of cells in the affected
710 tissue or organ (Alle *et al*, 2021). By restoring juvenile features to cells, it is easy to
711 understand reprogramming as an attractive rejuvenating strategy; cell reprogramming
712 was, in fact, shown to rejuvenate senescent and centenarian human cells (Lapasset
713 *et al*, 2011) and reduce the deleterious effects of ageing (Alle *et al.*, 2021; Simpson *et*
714 *al*, 2021), but limitations were found when proceeding to *in vivo* studies, concerning
715 teratoma formation, and limited lifespan has consequently been reported in mice (Alle
716 *et al.*, 2021). More recently, a new protocol of single short reprogramming reportedly
717 overcomes previous problems, successfully increasing lifespan in mice (Alle *et al*,
718 2022). With this short reprogramming, Alle *et al* prevented age-related tissue
719 deterioration in skin, kidney, lung, and spleen; it would be interestingly to see if this
720 procedure also ameliorates age related brain dysfunction.

721 Concerning the benefits of cellular reprogramming in age-related cognitive decline, *in*
722 *vivo* local reprogramming was found to ameliorate ageing features in the hippocampal
723 dentate gyrus, improving neuronal plasticity and memory in mice (Rodriguez-Matellan
724 *et al*, 2020). Since the nervous system has limited self-repair capacity, neuronal
725 replacement using cell reprogramming is an emerging, although technically very
726 challenging, field. Three approaches have arisen: recruitment of neural stem cell
727 (NSC) niches to produce neurons, reprogramming of local glial cells into neurons, and
728 transplantation of foetal progenitor cells. Various degrees of success have emerged
729 from studies of cellular reprogramming in animal models of neurodegenerative
730 diseases, recently extensively reviewed elsewhere (Clark *et al*, 2022). Research in
731 this field is emerging, and potentially contributing with new ways to restore CNS
732 function and increase healthspan.

733 **Conclusions**

734 Research in brain ageing still has many unanswered questions, such as: why are
735 some brain regions more affected than others?; what determines a healthy versus a
736 pathological ageing trajectory?; why is the rate of ageing in the brain different from
737 peripheral tissues?; can peripheral tissue, in fact, determine brain ageing?

738 In this review, we described the latest research addressing some of these questions.
739 Brain ageing, just like organismal ageing, is a complex network of processes, with the
740 multifaceted brain ageing mechanisms involving local age-related alterations and
741 systemic derived factors. Locally, brain cells, including neurons, glia, endothelial cells,
742 and stem cell niches, are exposed to age-related increase in DNA damage,
743 proteostasis dysfunction, mitochondria damage, accumulation of ROS, and
744 senescence; together, these factors are highly detrimental to tissue function.
745 Additionally, it is now well recognized that factors extrinsic to the CNS can have a
746 profound effect in brain health. As such, extrinsic, less invasive, systemic
747 manipulations altering the systemic environment, leading to a more youthful state of

748 blood or peripheric tissues, can effectively alter brain function and ameliorate age-
749 related brain dysfunction, promoting brain rejuvenation.

750 Since lifespan extension is only pertinent if accompanied by healthspan extension,
751 and, more importantly, by preserving brain health and cognition, finding systemic
752 rejuvenating strategies that act simultaneously in peripheral tissues and in brain
753 function is a valid strategy, and a major accomplishment, if achieved.

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755 Figures

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758 **Figure 1 – Hallmarks of brain ageing.** Scheme depicting the hallmarks of ageing in
759 the brain described in this review: genomic instability, telomere attrition, epigenetic
760 alterations, loss of proteostasis, dysregulated metabolism (including nutrient sensing
761 and mitochondrial dysfunction), cellular senescence, stem cell exhaustion, and altered
762 intercellular communication. The pyramidal illustration represents the primary
763 hallmarks (on the bottom), antagonistic (secondary) hallmarks emerging in response
764 to the primary hallmarks, and the tertiary integrative hallmarks, ultimately leading to
765 tissue homeostasis failures and dysfunction.

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Figure 2 – Impact of local and systemic ageing in brain health. Both neural cellular intrinsic factors and extrinsic systemic defects can contribute to the decline in brain function during ageing. Locally, brain cells can accumulate age-related damage, due to mitochondria dysfunction, oxidative stress, inflammation, or protein aggregation, which alters both neural cell survival but also core neural circuitry, and ultimately brain function. Systemic tissue ageing impacts brain health decline with age: periphery-derived factors such as inflammation mediators, SASP, peripheral immune invasion, and oxidative stress mediators that can reach the brain. ROS: reactive oxygen species; SASP: senescence associated secretory phenotype; BBB: blood-brain barrier.

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Figure 3 – Blood-brain barrier (BBB) dysfunction in ageing. The brain is protected from the periphery by the BBB, which maintains brain homeostasis by controlling the selective crossing of molecules. The BBB involves brain endothelial cells, mural cells (pericytes and vascular smooth muscle cells), astrocytes, neurons, microglia, and the basal lamina. BBB disruption in ageing is well documented, being a probable route for systemic factors, such as inflammatory mediators, cytokines, immune cells, and other molecules, to reach the brain and induce cellular and tissue dysfunction. ROS: reactive oxygen species; SASP: senescence associated secretory phenotype.

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Figure 4 - Rejuvenating strategies to improve brain health. Scheme illustrating systemic strategies found to be beneficial for brain health in ageing. With ageing comes damage accumulation in the organism, leading to increased organismal tissue dysfunction and inflammation. The brain is affected by the age-related accumulation of peripheral damage and also local damage, leading to morphological and functional alterations. Therapeutic interventions, such as heterochronic parabiosis, exercise, caloric restriction, counteracting senescence, and cellular reprogramming, have a positive effect counteracting the damage accumulation that leads to brain ageing by acting systemic and/or locally in the brain.

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